

Mining High School students' Cognitive Engagement from open responses on Machine Learning Practices *

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ABSTRACT

This is a work-in-progress research category paper. Open-ended questions are used to develop and capture students' cognitive engagement and are linked to an increase in language and aid in assessing aspects of student cognitive engagement. For this study, we present and compare Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning techniques for automatic detection of cognitive engagement in open-ended questions using popular classifiers. Using data from the StoryQ curriculum, we assessed $n = 28$ students' open-ended questions of three modules on machine learning practices. We evaluated students' cognitive engagement with a developed coding scheme adapted from two popular cognitive engagement frameworks. The $n = 840$ CE coded responses were used to train three machine learning classifiers (i.e., Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Decision Tree). The results showed that although each of the three classifiers scored better after tuning, Random Forest outperformed. However, the unbalanced dataset created challenges for the automatic classifier by misclassifying the higher engagement class. Additionally, to better understand cognitive engagement and students' literacy across the machine learning modules, we qualitatively analyzed students' responses by cross-recurrence quantification plots. We further compared students' cognitive engagement levels to the relationship between the indices of the cross-recurrence quantification analysis, and completion percentage as predictors. Our results revealed that completion percentage, along with the indices Recurrence Rate (RR), Number of Recurrence Lines (NRLINE), and Average Line Length (L), were significantly related to the student's cognitive engagement at both surface and deep levels. Based on the results from this study, scaffolding reading with engagement tasks, like open-ended questions, in teaching and learning on machine learning practices can produce higher levels of cognitive engagement and linguistic synchrony.

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folded reading with engagement tasks, like open-ended questions, in teaching and learning on machine learning practices can produce higher levels of cognitive engagement and linguistic synchrony.

Keywords

Cognitive Engagement, Literacy complexity, Automatic text classifier, Cross-Recurrence Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

Open-ended questions are a way to measure student cognitive engagement (CE) [47]. Although less explored, understanding cognitive engagement in computer science (CS) courses may help to reduce the high failure and dropout rate [10]. Open-ended questions develop and capture students' learning process by providing ways for students to elaborate on their thinking and construct knowledge by connecting past information with new information [33, 32]. In computer science education, open-ended questions are used to measure pedagogical content knowledge like understanding students' thinking related to programming [54]. Beyond survey data, open-ended questions are found to be effective in students' misconceptions related to a subject or topic [11] and have been used extensively in active learning approaches like problem-based learning and flipped classrooms.

In [11] study, researchers surveyed students on their learning and motivation during three approaches: lecture, problem-based learning (PBL), and flipped classroom. Although PBL and flipped classrooms were found to be more motivating for the students, the Instructors were worried about the time it takes to grade activities, specifically open-ended questions. Due to overhead constraints the flipped classroom instructor was unable to grade the open-ended questions until right before class. Waiting until longer to grade open-ended questions reduces the assessment time to help struggling students. Furthermore, manual coding used to identify students' CE from their answers to open-ended questions is demanding and time-consuming for Instructors [3]. Promoting an automated classifier of students' responses according to their CE scores may pose a solution to the issue.

Moreover, open-ended questions offer linguistic advantages by using abstract language skills such as predicting, analyzing

ing, and inferring [52]. By answering cognitively challenging open-ended questions, newly learned words and concepts help to develop language [6]. Since CE is naturally unobservable, researchers can detect this construct from students' use of verbal language or written materials [29]. Text mining has been used to evaluate CE in student writing through Linguistic Inquiry, and Word Count (LIWC), and measuring how engaged students are in a conversation or activity [41]. Although there are many studies in the literature on CE in fields such as science, MOOC, discussion, and PBL [11], there was limited research in the area of computer science education.

For this study, we aim to understand two areas of CE through open-ended questions and its impact on Machine Learning Practices (MLP) in a High School AI curriculum. First, we investigate whether CE can be inferred from open-ended data using popular algorithms. Second, we compare students' cognitive engagement levels to linguistic indices of cognitive dynamics to the quality of self-explanation. These findings will provide methodological and theoretical insights that can support Instructors and learners in understanding the roles of cognitive engagement and linguistic characteristics of cognitive engagement in Machine Learning practices.

2. BACKGROUND

To inform CE levels in students' open-ended questions we use an adapted ICAP framework with Bloom's Taxonomy indicators as our theoretical background to inform the labeling of student answers, as is a common practice in other studies [36]. Whilst understanding the CE levels of students we qualitatively analyzed students' linguistic synchrony by cross-recurrence quantification (CRQA) plots to observe linguistic cues of engagement and synchrony.

2.1 Cognitive Engagement

There are varying definitions for CE in the literature, like those involving psychological investment and effort through student motivation and strategies [44], students' investment in learning [53, 18]. Generally, CE involves the thinking that students do while engaged in academic learning tasks [24]. Studies have measured CE through scales [22], surveys, and self-report questionnaires [48]. However, assessing CE through self-reporting measures and behavioral assessment is complex [20]. CE has been linked to academic performance [22], self-efficacy [51], involvement experience [1], self-regulation [7], students' motivation [9, 22, 45], and literacy learning [50]. For example, [50] investigated a framework of instruction maximizing cognitive engagement in literacy learning with 88 teachers and nine students in nine high-poverty school classrooms across the United States. The study found that higher-level questioning contributed to students' improvement in reading comprehension and fluency and that time-on-task was positively related to students' gains in standardized reading comprehension in grades 2-5, whereas passive responding was negatively related. For our study, we define CE as students' mental and cognitive effort to comprehend material and concepts and complete assigned tasks [20].

2.2 Cognitive Engagement Frameworks

Bloom's taxonomy is a common framework for evaluating the cognitive levels of students' answers to open-ended ques-

tions [4, 8]. [4] and team updated Bloom's taxonomy to categorize questions and activities according to their cognitive levels of process dimension by changing the nouns to verbs and placing creation to the highest level in the taxonomy [26]. The cognitive domains from lower to higher order include remembering (able to recall information such as ideas, definitions, and theories); understanding (able to express the meaning of information in own words); applying (able to apply knowledge or skills to new situations); analyzing, (able to show and explain the relationships among parts); evaluating, (able to judge or assess the value of material and methods for a given purpose); and creating (able to connect and build relationships for new situations) [4, 8]. [19] used Bloom's to determine the levels of student thinking by analyzing and coding the cognitive processes students used when engaged in mobile learning. They found that students used cognitive processing at all six Blooms levels, for example, they were engaged in remembering activities 8.9% of the time, using understanding 32.7% of the time, applied knowledge 15.8% of the time, engaging in analysis 7.9% of the time, evaluating 3% of the time and created knowledge 31.7% of the time.

[15] ICAP framework is largely based on overt behaviors, and depending on what overt behaviors students are engaged in, they will exhibit Passive, Active, Constructive, or Interactive modes. Passive is the lowest level of engagement (paying attention but not 'overtly' doing anything else), Active CE means applying and integrating new information from prior information (while new information is being applied to similar but nonidentical contexts), and Constructive CE includes generative behaviors (containing new ideas that go beyond the original information given) [15]. The ICAP framework includes an Interactive mode that must include one of the following (a) both partners' utterances must be primarily constructive, and (b) a sufficient degree of turn-taking must occur. Our study did not include these activities; therefore, the Interactive mode was omitted from our study.

ICAP frameworks have so far been predominantly used to analyze and improve teachers' instructional approach in K12 STEM education. [13] the study investigated students' learning improvement by asking their teacher to prompt them according to a passive, active or constructive mode in a one-on-one learning environment and found higher student learning and engagement in the setting of constructive mode. [27] demonstrated that a teacher-centered approach would result in passive student engagement, while student-centered teaching correlates with higher-level engagement. The ICAP framework has further been used as a tool to differentiate learning outcomes [25], as a base to develop test questions for high school students [37], and to analyze students' responses in STEM college courses. While this qualitative approach is time-consuming, [21] explored the possibility of automatically capturing the level of cognitive engagement in online course discussion forums in automatic classifiers. In their study, the authors developed a predictive model working with a mix of ICAP and Bloom's taxonomy [21]. Their findings demonstrate that a correct automated analysis of cognitive engagement in online learning environments is possible [21].

Table 1: Cognitive Engagement Label Coding Scheme

Label	ICAP Level	Description	Bloom's Indicator	EXAMPLE: What is one strategy you can use to determine what features someone has used to build a classification model?
2	Interactive	New information is integrated with activated prior knowledge, and new knowledge is inferred	Transfer	"You can look at the data set and find words that really stand out to you or words that have a strong emotional connotation. You can also check the graph and the probability in terms of the features being used or how strongly they correlate with the result."
1	Active	Behaviors that cause-focused attention while manipulating	Understand and Apply	"You can test multiple reviews with words that you think may be the features to determine if they are actually features."
0	Passive	Overt activities that are carried out mindlessly	Recall and Store	"I can use major words that people say in reviews first. Words like love, hate, bad, ,delicious, and more."

2.3 Linguistic Synchrony

Linguistic synchrony or shared language [5] is aligned representations across phonological, syntactic, semantic, and situational levels where one level reinforces other levels to enhance the overall perception of synchrony [49]. Aligning language representations allows for either intentionally or subconsciously creating a common ground, "such as matching a cognitive framework in which conversants adopt shared assumptions, linguistic referents and knowledge" [30]. Linguistic synchrony is connected to common knowledge building [5], dialog interactions [49] and extend to linguistic immediacy [35] where features of language can provide insight into the relationship between communicants. For instance, studies have shown that individuals produce utterances that match the grammatical structure of sentences they have recently heard or read [30]. Another study showed that students automatically match the language style of an essay question [30].

More importantly, repetition phenomena tend to be strong linguistic cues of engagement and synchrony [43]. We thus hypothesize that a higher cognitive engagement will simultaneously go hand in hand with higher linguistic synchrony. Although studies have confirmed a strong link between cognitive engagement, linguistics [24] and literacy skills [39, 50], the link between cognitive engagement and linguistic synchrony is, to our knowledge, first introduced by this study. Thus, this study investigates the relationship between CE and linguistic synchrony by evaluating CRQA indices to understand students' deepness of learning within MLP.

3. LINGUISTIC SYNCHRONY AND CRQA

Cross-recurrence quantification analysis (CRQA) is a Machine Learning technique based on dynamic correlation that utilizes an unsupervised machine-learning method (k-means clustering) to identify repeating connectivity patterns [42]. For our study we will use CRQA and statistical analysis to measure the linguistic synchrony of students cognitive engagement in Machine Learning practices. [3] first illustrated dynamic text analyses with computational techniques from dynamical systems, using CRQA. The authors' research connected cognitive dynamics to the quality of self-explanation. Connecting the idea that when a person reads a text pas-

sively, the person will explain the meaning of the text without referencing the previous material in the text or outside knowledge. However, if a person reads a text "deeper," that person can connect with previous material and develop a deeper understanding of the concepts in the text. Additionally, [3] found that the number of lines and word count were strong predictors of comprehension test scores, explaining that comprehension processes of skilled and less skilled readers can be differentiated.

4. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

There are two parts to this study. The first part is to evaluate various classifiers to determine which one would be suitable to automatically classify CE from open-ended questions in three modules on machine learning practices. Our coding scheme on the ICAP framework includes three cognitive categories: Passive, Active, and Constructive [15]. Additionally, we informed the coding scheme with Bloom's revised taxonomy [4] by mapping Bloom's taxonomy level indicators onto the ICAP cognitive engagement indicators. The self-written responses were manually scored from 0-2 using the rubric in Table 1. For example, the Blooms level Transfer indicator informs ICAP Constructive category, Bloom's Understand and Apply indicator informs the Active category, and finally, Bloom's Recall and Store informs the Passive category in ICAP.

Based on the coding scheme, we first identified whether students' answers were repeating verbatim from the teaching materials by only recalling. Then, we evaluated whether "knowledge can be applied to similar but nonidentical contexts" [15] by exhibiting reasoning, argumentation, or elaboration on a topic. Finally, we evaluated whether students created new knowledge beyond what was provided in the learning materials by inferring or transferring knowledge. While coding the posts, we assigned the highest engagement level observed in each answer.

The second part of this study investigates linguistic synchrony by evaluating CRQA indices to understand students' deepness of learning within MLP and observe the relation to CE. We hypothesize that students with higher cognitive engagement in their open-ended responses will also have higher

linguistic synchrony through the CRQA-reported indices. Meaning that those that are more cognitively engaged in the MLP curriculum will use substantive language in their answers. Our research questions are as follows:

RQ1. What model will best automatically classify open-ended answers based on the cognitive engagement level?

RQ2. What are the characteristics of linguistic synchrony and students' cognitive engagement in Machine Learning Practices?

5. METHOD

5.1 Data and Context

The context of this study was a high school journalism class in the Northeastern United States. The teacher of the class participated in a professional development (PD) workshop on AI for four weeks. In this workshop, the teacher experienced the StoryQ AI curriculum as a learner in the StoryQ learning environment [12]. The curriculum includes eight different learning modules that do not require prior coding or programming experience. After the PD, the teacher decided to integrate seven learning modules into her Journalism classroom for three weeks (45 minutes class for each day). Students from any grade level were welcome to participate in this elective class. The class included twenty-eight students from diverse backgrounds regarding their grade level and race/ethnicity (i.e., thirteen 12th-grade students, eight 11th-grade students, and two 10th-grade students with 54% Black/African, 15% Hispanic, 20% White/Caucasian, 6% other and 6% didn't answer). In each class, the teacher presented key concepts related to daily activities, and then asked students to complete the activities either individually or as pairs. While students were completing the learning activities, they answered activity specific questions. For example, in the "Features and Models" activity, students experienced feature engineering by identifying specific features and building machine learning models. When they were completing this activity, they answered activity-specific questions like "Compare the two graphs and explain how the feature "great" affected the model?". For this study, we particularly analyzed 30 open-ended questions to have a deep understanding of students' machine learning practices in the three modules (5) Sentiment analysis, (6) Features and models, and (7) All the words as features

5.2 Automatic Classification of Cognitive Engagement in Machine Learning Practices

5.2.1 Data Coding Procedure

The self-written responses were scored from 0-2 on the adapted IACP framework using the rubric in Table 1. First, two doctoral students reviewed the Cognitive Engagement coding scheme, coded 40 threads independently, and calculated the initial inter-rater reliability (IRR) using the Inter-rated Agreement Cohens Kappa [17, 23] and reached a score of 65%. After reviewing the disagreements, they coded 40 more together. Finally, the two raters independently scored a subset of 10% of the self-written responses and achieved acceptable reliability (Cohen's kappa = .844). The most experienced rater then scored the remainder of the self-explanations for n = 840.

5.2.2 Data Preprocessing

To build a cognitive engagement classifier, we localized variables; id, feature, and label. Next, we randomized our data and split it into training (80%, n = 694), and evaluation (20%, n = 173) sets. We ran several pre-processing steps using Python to transform raw data into a form for the algorithms to work. We performed data cleaning on the feature variable to remove empty rows and case folding to convert all characters into lowercase, expanding contractions, removing punctuation and stopwords, and stemming. We removed NAs and applied Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (tf-idf) to identify the importance of the word in the text and then applied Count Vectorization giving our final feature in the supervised task a bag of words. After processing, our training dataset consists of n= 547 and an evaluation dataset of n= 138 (without the label variable). The training dataset label variable includes counts for Passive (0) = 270, Active (1) = 242, and Constructive (2) = 35 cognitive engagement.

5.2.3 Model Selection

Initially, we chose the classification models Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Extra Trees, Ada Boost, Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, and Logistic Regression as ideal for classification modeling [38]. We evaluate and compare each accuracy and performance as an initial baseline. We selected Random Forest, SVM, and Decision Trees for their higher performance rate and Kappa after analyzing the confusion matrix. Furthermore, in the literature, when thresholds are adjusted, they provide excellent precision [28]. We noticed that for the Constructive CE class, the models included zeros for Precision, Recall, and F1. We noticed our models are classified into two classes, Passive (0) and Active(1), not three. Therefore, we decided to tune parameters to see if we could maximize the model performance.

5.2.4 Model Tuning

Initially, we changed n estimators and cross-validation through trial and error before conducting Grid Search [31, 40] to locate the most accurate hyperparameters as can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Hyperparameters

ML Classifier	Parameters	Values
Support Vector Machine(SVM)	Kernel	'linear', 'sigmoid', 'poly', 'rbf'
	C	0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000
	gamma	1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001
Random Forrest (RF)	Number of estimators	6, 12, 24, 36
	Criterion	'gini', 'entropy'
	Max depth	range(2, 20, 1)
	Min samples leaf	range(1, 10, 1)
	Min samples split	range(2, 10, 1)
	Max features bootstrap	'auto', 'log2'
Decision Tree	bootstrap	True
	Criterion	'gini', 'entropy']
	Max depth	range(1, 10)
	Min samples split	range(1, 10)
	Min samples leaf	range(1, 5)

5.2.5 Model Comparison and Error Analysis

For all three models we provide performance measures (Precision, Recall, and F1) in Table 3 by cognitive engagement level. Precision calculates the accuracy for the minority class. Precision in unbalanced models is calculated as the sum of true positives across all classes divided by the sum

of true positives and false positives across all classes. Recall quantifies the number of correct positive predictions made out of all positive predictions that could have been made. Recall is calculated as the sum of true positives across all classes divided by the sum of true positives and false negatives across all classes. According to [31, 40], when minimizing the number of false positives maximizing precision should be of focus, whereas maximizing the recall will minimize the number of false negatives. Therefore, for the unbalanced set, looking at the F1 score is optimal. The F1 score is the mean of precision and recall. Interpreting the confusion matrix allows us to understand how the classifier misclassifies and where.

Table 3: Performance Measures

Type	SVM			Random Forest			Decision Tree		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
Passive	.75	.65	.70	.82	.82	.82	.74	.65	.69
Active	.56	.70	.60	.70	.77	.73	.59	.68	.63
Constructive	0	0	0	0	0	0	.17	.17	.17
Weighted	.64	.64	.63	.74	.77	.75	.65	.64	.64

5.2.6 Results

Initially, we chose the classification models Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Extra Trees, Ada Boost, Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, and Logistic Regression. We notice the distribution of the dataset shows skewness towards Constructive CE because the dataset is unbalanced, with the lowest number of 35 in Constructive CE. For this reason, we evaluated additional metrics besides accuracy and Kappa, for example, the confusion matrix, precision, recall, and F1 (Table 3). Random Forest, SVM, and Decision Trees had higher performance metrics and Kappa after analyzing the confusion matrix. We settled on using these three to hypertune and evaluate performance further.

To answer RQ1: What model will best automatically classify open-ended answers based on the cognitive engagement level?

We hypertuned the classifiers with Grid Search, using the hyperparameters in Table 2. We found the best-performing model for SVM was obtained with kernel = ‘rbf’ and (C) = 0.1 and achieved 77% accuracy received on the test set. The best model obtained for RF includes max depth = 18, criterion = ‘gini’, and the number of estimators = 36, and achieved 75% accuracy on the test set. Finally, the best model achieved for the Decision Tree includes criterion = Entropy, max depth = 8, max samples split = 3, and min samples leaf = 6, and an accuracy score of 70%.

Further analysis with Cochran’s test revealed statistically significant differences between the classifiers we built, $Q = 389.1$, $p < .001$. The Random Forest F1 outperforms in the Passive and Active classes. However, the Decision Tree model is the only model classified into the Constructive minority class. We notice that Random Forest has the lowest misclassification for the Active and Passive categories. The true positive rate in the Random Forest classifier was 73% for the Active answers. Thus, the classifier missed 27% of the Active answers that should have been labeled Active but labeled them as Passive. Looking at the Confusion Matrix there are 13 answers misclassified as Passive, and 44 were

correctly identified. In the Constructive category, six were misclassified into Active. As is the same for the SVM classifier. Random Forest was our best model and demonstrated accuracy (77%) and Cohen’s kappa values ($K = .55$).

We recognize in this analysis that although Random Forest performed well, we only used one feature to categorize CE and only categorized it into two classes. The misclassification is most likely due to the small amount of labeled data compared to the other two courses with >200 labels. Additionally, using one feature may need to be more robust for written responses, including additional features such as content knowledge scoring.

A predictive classifier can add value as it will reduce an instructor’s overhead, support student learning with real-time feedback or course intervention, resulting in an increase of students’ academic performance [22], self-efficacy [51], involvement experience [1], self-regulation [7], students’ motivation [9, 22, 45], and literacy learning [50].

For instance, this type of classifier would offer opportunities for educators to add classifying open-ended questions to a Dashboard where they can monitor their students’ engagement level throughout the modules in real-time. A dashboard using the classifier for open-ended questions would give a warning to those with passive engagement. The instructor could apply interventions such as adjusting their teaching or learning practices to support student success. However, educators may be hesitant to use a dashboard monitoring tool where there is doubt about the inconsistency of classification. Therefore more research is needed to optimize the classifier for all three classes.

However, a predictive classifier would need to yield consistent and reliable results in order for Instructors to be able rely on them. Therefore, more research is needed to optimize the classifier for all three cases in order to determine which model will best automatically classify open-ended answers.

5.3 Measurement of Linguistic Synchrony in Machine Learning Practices

5.3.1 Preprocessing

To generate and quantify the recurrence plots, each module question was combined into a single aggregated question—the same for students’ written responses. Additionally, in Python, pre-processing the text data included removing punctuation, converting to lowercase, tokenization, removing stop words, stemming, and assigning a numerical code. Since CRQA requires equal lengths for both question and answer of each student, we equalized the length by adding artificial tokens to the shorter length between each pair of exchanges. We plot the visualization and interpret the results using Posit’s (formerly R) CRQA package.

5.3.2 Cross Recurrence Quantification Analysis

Based on recurrence theory, CRQA provides “an evaluation of synchronization or coordination” [34]. [34] further explains that “when two signals access the same regions of a state space simultaneously, their transitory coordination occurs at high rates of recurrence” (p.4). This allows recurrence-based analyses to quantify the dynamical struc-

ture to capture coupling properties underlying leader-follower relationships [16]. Where the dynamics of an individual time series in univariate RQA look at one-time series, the cross-recurrence now reflects the coupled dynamics of the two-time series [46]. Cross-recurrences around the main diagonal are absent or sparse if the series is not synchronized. The main advantage of using CRQA is quantifying the dynamics of a time series based on the patterns of recurrence points found in the plot. To do this, we calculated the recurrences to create a square matrix.

For our study, the CRQA metrics that quantify the recurrence visualization include Recurrence Rate (RR), Determinism (DET), Number of Recurrence Lines (NRLINE), the average length of line structures (maxL), and normalized Entropy (rENTR) [34, 16, 46, 3]. Recurrence Rate (RR) measures the density of points represented in a recurrence plot. For instance, CRQA determines how often the students' written response mimics the number of repeated words divided by the product of the student's response and the question being asked (RR). Determinism (DET) provides information about the distribution of the recurrent points [3, 2]. DET evaluates the percentage of times a student and a question use the same words out of all the recurrence points. NRLINE calculates the length of the longest diagonal line in the recurrence plot. rENTR is calculated as the Shannon entropy of the distribution of the line lengths in the recurrence plot [3, 2]. It can be considered a measure of the predictability and regularity of the interaction between the two-factor series, whereas higher rENTR results in worse DET reliability[34].

5.3.3 Results and Discussion

RQ2. What are the characteristics of linguistic synchrony and students' cognitive engagement in Machine Learning practices?

Our analysis found Max Word Length, Recurrence Rate (RR), Number of Recurrence Lines, and Max Lines would be good linguistic characteristics of cognitive engagement in Machine Learning practices as per Pearson Correlation in Table 4.

We qualitatively examine students' recurrence plots evaluating patterns of students in Low CE, Middle CE, and High CE to understand the predictive characteristics from the Pearson Correlation. We notice Figure 1's complex patterning compared to Figure 2. The characteristics indicated that those of higher CE have a higher RR, and those of lower CE have a lower RR. The density of points of Figure 1's RR are close together and very dense compared to Figure 2's density points which are sparse and further apart. Similarly, the max word length is higher in students with higher CE along with NRLINE and MaxL. For example, in Fig 1 and 2, the recurrence plots for questions and answers of students who are of high (a) and low (b) cognitive engagement correspond with denser points indicating a higher Recurrence Rate (RR) where questions and students share the exact same words. Fig 1 (a) has a higher RR at 1.21, but the student of low CE only has a RR of 0.57. Additionally, the NRLINE (the Number of marked points constructing diagonal lines) is 159 in higher CE (Fig 1) compared to 20 in lower CE (Fig 2). With closer inspection, we notice that Fig 1 repeats more

words (shown below) from the question, which would add to a higher Recurrence Rate as is consistent in other studies [3].

Fig 1 Q: "Compare the two graphs above. How do you think the feature "great" affected the model?" A: "I think the feature great affected the model by model 2 having more positive reviews being recognized. Model 1 has less positive reviews being recognized because it's less accurate"

Fig 2 Q: "Compare the two graphs above. How do you think the feature "great" affected the model?" A: "the actual results were more than the predicted"

It is notable that even with this added increase, the substantive answer is greater in linguistic complexity than the limited answer from fig 2. Another exciting result of Fig 1 is that they had a high DET compared to their peers within the higher CE category. Other students that identified with high CE had lower DET than the low CE students. Fig 1 repeats the exact words from the questions more often as part of the given answer.

Lastly, we computed a Pearson Correlation on the RQA characteristics to quantify the structure found in recurrence plots. Our analysis shows that Max Word Length, Recurrence Rate (RR), Number of Recurrence Lines, and Max Lines have a linear relationship with Cognitive Engagement. RR and CE revealed a moderate positive correlation, $r(26) = .41$, $p = .028$. Max word length and CE showed a large positive correlation, $r(26) = .94$, $p < .001$. NRLINE and CE revealed a large positive correlation, $r(26) = .63$, $p < .001$, and MaxL and CE revealed a moderate positive correlation, $r(26) = .47$, $p = .01$. The analysis indicates better writers produce answers that contained a higher quantity of recurrent sequences (maxL), as well as longer recurrent sequences, on average (Entropy) [2].

The findings are consistent with the connection that passive reading would relate to low cognitive engagement at the passive level. Still, deeper reading would show in a student's answer by connecting text material to outside knowledge leading to higher cognitive engagement. The findings are consistent with [3] findings explaining that comprehension processes of skilled and less skilled readers can be differentiated.

Table 4: Correlations of RQA Indices with CE mean

Indices	Mean	SD	SE	P
MaxW	355.11	71.99	13.60	0.000
RR	0.69	0.24	0.05	0.028
NRLINE	38.21	31.19	5.90	0.000
MaxL	4.39	2.01	0.38	0.011
L	2.20	0.16	0.03	0.111
Entropy	0.44	0.23	0.04	0.107
DET	8.51	2.81	0.53	0.304

6. CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

23

Figure 1: Recurrence plot for a series of answers to be of high CE ($M = .96$). RQA indices for this recurrence plot: $RR = 1.21$, $DET = 14.19$, $NRLINE = 159$.

3

Figure 2: Recurrence plot for a series of answers to be of low CE ($M = .22$). RQA indices for this recurrence plot: $RR = 0.57$, $DET = 9.59$, $NRLINE = 20$.

In conclusion, open-ended questions offer rich information about students' cognitive engagement and literacy complexity. However, grading open-ended questions by hand in a CS course is time consuming. Deploying a multi-class classifi-

cation algorithm could be a solution to identify struggling students in a timely fashion. However, much work still needs to be done.

In terms of limitations, an area for improvement would be to recode the open-ended responses with a more robust coding scheme. We recognized that we coded each answer within one of the three ICAP modes. In the future, adding categories within each mode may add to the features for identifying student answers.

Since our data was unbalanced, the classifiers had difficulties identifying the Constructive (2) class. This could have led to our model underfitting. Improving the accuracy as well as the performance of classification is essential [14]. A more robust coding scheme and adding the predictors from the indices may increase the class that was misclassified due to an imbalance in the data set. However, further research is needed before adopting the indices as features for model prediction, as the model may contain linguistic bias.

Many educators teach reading and writing separately. However, students with high linguistic synchrony may exhibit linguistic complexity by applying what they read to a piece of writing. Further research investigating open-ended questions that promote linguistic complexity in student answers would aid educators in monitoring students' cognitive engagement through their writing.

Finally, it might be worth researching how additional NLP categories would aid in identifying CE, such as parts-of-speech and semantic information.

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